

SZÉCHENYI 2020

European Union
European Regional
Development Fund

INVESTING IN YOUR FUTURE

R&D SUMMARY AND RESULTS PRESENTATION

BREEDING OF ORNAMENTAL PLANTS AND
DEVELOPMENT OF PROPAGATION
TECHNOLOGY

02.01.2018 – 31.12.2019

Our company implemented a research and development project for **ornamental plant breeding and propagation technology development** as part of the **GINOP-2.1.7-15 (15-2016-01104)** grant for **prototype, product, technology, and service development**.

As part of the project, we planned to develop the prototype breeding and propagation technology for **Laburnum anagyroides (Golden Chain Tree)** and **Prunus cerasifera (Columnar Red-Leaf Plum)**. The primary methods of our breeding activities were **heterosis breeding and clonal selection** for variety development. After selecting suitable parent plants, we produced multiple generations of offspring, continuously selecting them over several years based on climatic adaptability and ornamental value. After this, the most promising varieties were identified and subjected to **testing processes**, where we selected the best strains based on **phenotypic and measurable parameters**.

Following the grant submission, we commenced **professional breeding and selection work**, which resulted in the development of the best clones. The candidate varieties are being examined according to **UPOV (International Union for the Protection of New Varieties of Plants) guidelines**.

Laburnum anagyroides 'Yellow Rocket' (Columnar Golden Chain Tree)

The **Laburnum anagyroides 'Yellow Rocket' (LAYR)** variety was submitted for **international plant variety protection (CPVO)**, and after completing the official examination, it was granted international protection under the **CPVO number 57653 on March 15, 2021**.

This variety has a **columnar growth habit**, which makes it fundamentally different from previously known golden chain tree varieties. It is

significantly **slimmer and requires less space**, making it highly valuable among gardeners and landscapers. Its compact growth allows it to be an attractive ornamental choice even for **small gardens**.

Even at a young age, this plant produces **abundant flowers**, giving it a distinctive appearance. It thrives in calcareous, warm, and loose soils and prefers **sunlight** (Schmidt-Tóth, 1996). Due to **climate change**, the importance of this variety is increasing, as it benefits from the **shifting climatic conditions**.

Thanks to the **variety protection**, our company can control **propagation rights internationally**. This ensures that only plants with propagating material produced or authorized by our company enter both domestic and international markets. Additionally, our company is entitled to collect **variety protection fees**, further enhancing our competitiveness.

Our partner, **Breederplants V.O.F.**, presented the **Laburnum anagyroides 'Yellow Rocket'** at the **2019 Green is Life exhibition in Warsaw**, where it gained international attention. Market research was conducted, leading to negotiations with growers from the **Netherlands, Poland, and England**. The findings indicated significant **interest and propagation intentions** among producers.

We have also showcased this variety at **domestic nursery exhibitions**, and the sale of our **own propagated plants** has begun, supporting the **business activities and competitiveness** of our company. **Early feedback** suggests that customers **appreciate this plant**, and they are willing to pay a **higher price compared to similar varieties**.

Our company is responsible for **propagating the Laburnum variety** and selling it both in **retail and wholesale markets**.

Prunus cerasifera hybrid (Columnar Red-Leaf Plum)

Our **Prunus variety** is a **hybrid plum tree with red foliage and a columnar growth habit**, but it has a **slow growth rate** and is expected to **remain smaller** than the **species' original form**. Its **novelty lies in the combination of columnar growth and red leaf coloration**, which are typically found in separate varieties on the market.

This variety originates from a **phenotypically hybrid local strain (cv. Colos) resulting from open pollination**. Additionally, it is a cross between **Prunus cerasifera 'Woodii'**, a highly popular ornamental plum variety. We developed this new clone by selecting from **hybrid offspring** produced from these **two parent plants**.

The variety has **dark red-black twigs**, which distinguish it from other cultivars. Its **flowers are pink**, and its **leaves are dark burgundy**. It **does not bear fruit**, and based on our current knowledge, it is **sterile due to its hybrid origin and ploidy level**.

This characteristic is particularly significant for **urban landscaping**, as it eliminates **fruit drop issues**, which can attract insects and create mess on sidewalks. The **columnar growth habit** makes it ideal for **narrow spaces and urban tree planting**, such as along streets or in small private gardens.

Climate change favors this variety as well, as it **tolerates heat and drought well**. To maintain its **intense red foliage**, it must be planted in **full sun**, further expanding its usability. Importantly, it **has shown no susceptibility to sunburn or scorching symptoms**.

There is already **considerable interest** in the **Columnar Red-Leaf Plum**, and its **propagation and market introduction** are the **next key steps**. Our **Dutch partner** is currently **testing the variety under Dutch growing conditions** based on a **test agreement**. The **initial promising results** and **high interest** suggest that **international variety protection registration** is now in progress.

Our company presented the varieties at domestic professional exhibitions in 2019, including the nursery fair in Szombathely organized by the Hungarian Nursery Growers Association and the nursery fair in Kecskemét organized by the Hungarian Nurserymen's Association. Unfortunately, in 2020, the professional exhibitions were canceled due to the pandemic. Since 2021, we have been showcasing the varieties at the newly held nursery exhibitions. We have observed strong interest in the varieties at every exhibition. Currently, we are multiplying the Prunus variety so that after obtaining international plant variety protection, we will immediately have plants ready for sale.

An important aspect of the product development undertaken as part of the project is the modernization of the propagation technology for the new varieties. Our main goal is to build a highly efficient propagation facility, which has an area of 12m x 4m and is equipped with electric soil heating (bottom heating) with adjustable temperature. As part of the project, we have also set up a solar panel system that produces the necessary amount of energy to operate the bottom heating during the spring. The green energy collected and produced by the solar panels helps reduce the ecological footprint of our company and lowers costs even after the project is completed. It significantly contributes to circular economy practices and sustainability. The required humidity for rooting is maintained by an automatic humidifier system.

After the propagation equipment was completed, we were able to begin propagation experiments, which we are continuing in order to achieve the best possible rooting rate. We have tested the soil heating and its controllability multiple times, conducting soil temperature measurements, during which we determined that the equipment can be controlled precisely and effectively. The humidity control is sufficiently regulated, allowing for the creation and maintenance of the required humidity for rooting. The equipment also enables the production of larger quantities of propagation material from other species that are difficult to root, which will significantly impact the future success of the business.

The experiences gained during the propagation experiments can also be applied to the propagation of plants grown in our nursery, contributing to more efficient nursery operations. Through our own production of propagation material, we will be able to propagate species or varieties that we could not have propagated before the project, as we would have had to purchase them from external suppliers.

Autovegetative propagations were conducted based on the maturity of the shoots for the *Laburnum* and *Prunus* genera. Propagations were also performed on the mother plants and already rooted stock. We carried out the propagation in cell trays with a peat-perlite mixture. Hardwood cuttings were taken in February–March. The cuttings were treated on a heated base at 18°C for 3 weeks. The cuttings were collected in January and stored in a cooler until propagation. Rooting hormone treatments were applied using Germon C (0.5 mg), Dip 'n Grow (5000 ppm), and Clonex rooting agents, with three repetitions. Green cuttings were performed in July using a misting system. The cuttings were trimmed to two or three buds, and the leaves were partially trimmed back.

Rooting occurred successfully in the propagation trials, although the heated base treatment had a more negative effect, which is why it was not used in later experiments. The trays were hardened outdoors and then potted. The growth of the rooted plants is satisfactory.

Results:

In the project, we planned to develop the breeding and technological improvements necessary for the propagation of two prototypes: *Laburnum* (golden rain) and *Prunus* (red-column plum).

We aimed to develop two prototype products that would be suitable for domestic and community patents. One of these products already holds international plant variety protection (CPVO), while the process for the other variety is currently ongoing, along with the preparatory steps preceding it.

**CERTIFICATE ON THE GRANT OF
COMMUNITY PLANT VARIETY RIGHTS**

THE COMMUNITY PLANT VARIETY OFFICE HEREBY ACKNOWLEDGES THE GRANT OF COMMUNITY PLANT VARIETY RIGHT BY ITS DECISION N° EU 57653 OF 15 MARCH 2021 TAKEN IN ACCORDANCE WITH COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) N° 2100/94 ON COMMUNITY PLANT VARIETY RIGHTS, WITH EFFECT FROM THE DATE OF THE DECISION REFERRED TO ABOVE, FOR

Kiss Kertesz Duo Ltd.
041/37 PN
HU - 6042 Fülöphaza

AS HOLDER OF THIS RIGHT,

REPRESENTED BY

Breederplants V.O.F.

BEING DOMICILED OR HAVING HIS SEAT OR ESTABLISHMENT IN

Botterwerf 14
NL - 2804 MK Gouda

IN RESPECT OF THE VARIETY OF *Laburnum anagyroides* Medik. BEARING THE DESIGNATED DENOMINATION:

'LAYR'

FOR A PERIOD EXPIRING ON 31 DECEMBER 2051 AT THE LATEST.

THE COMMUNITY PLANT VARIETY RIGHT HAS UNIFORM EFFECT WITHIN THE TERRITORY OF THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITY AND MAY NOT BE TRANSFERRED IN RESPECT OF THIS TERRITORY OTHERWISE THAN ON SUCH UNIFORM BASIS. IT CAN BE EXERCISED AND ENJOYED BY THE HOLDER IN ACCORDANCE WITH COUNCIL REGULATION N° 2100/94 ON COMMUNITY PLANT VARIETY RIGHTS.

THIS ACKNOWLEDGEMENT DOES NOT AFFECT THE REQUIREMENT OF THE HOLDER TO PAY THE FEES DUE FOR EACH YEAR OF DURATION OF THE COMMUNITY PLANT VARIETY RIGHT.

President of the
Community Plant Variety Office

The steps for developing prototypes of the two different plant varieties were completely identical, as both varieties are temperate zone, woody ornamental plants. These prototypes can be selected in our country, are climate-tolerant, easy to manage, disease-resistant, and will also be marketable internationally. The ornamental plant variety offerings in regions with similar climates to ours are lacking species and varieties that are resistant to climate change and new biotic and abiotic stresses. Our goal was to provide the market with so-called sustainable varieties. Due to the changing, warming climate and increasing air pollution, there is a growing international demand for urban tree planting, which generates further interest in new, adaptable varieties. Based on data from research institutions, nurseries, and the plant variety database, we selected varieties suitable for breeding that can perform well in international markets.

Due to climate change and the increasing effects of urbanization, enhancing public space plantings and ensuring long-term sustainability in urban environments is a critical issue in Hungary. The *Kiss Kertész Duó Kft.* nursery in Fülöpháza, with its climatic and soil conditions, is an excellent model for the environmental and climatic extremes found in Hungary. The increasing summer heat, the rapid rise of heatwave days, the unpredictability of winter frosts, extreme weather events, sandy, poor-quality soils, and drought periods pose significant challenges in plant application as well. Domestic plant breeding must meet these challenges. One possible solution for environmental adaptation breeding is our nursery located near Fülöpháza. This nursery is ideally suited for adaptation and selection breeding in terms of its territorial and ecological conditions. Innovation development experiments can be successfully carried out here. The desired goals of product development will be pursued in this area. The results achieved here can be widely applied in domestic areas and in regions with similar sensitive ecological conditions.

Project Implementation Period:

Project start date: 2018.01.02.

Physical project completion date: 2019.12.31.

Quantitative Results of the Project:

Year	Domestic sales revenue	Export sales revenue	Total
2021	950 600 Ft	670 853 Ft	1 621 453 Ft
2022	2 385 249 Ft	2 069 819 Ft	4 455 068 Ft
2023	349 691 Ft	801 752 Ft	1 151 443 Ft
Total:	3 685 540 Ft	2 820 844 Ft	7 227 964 Ft

We achieved the revenue target set in the application and even significantly exceeded it (by approximately double). The project successfully met the committed monitoring indicators.

References:

1: Díszfaiskola: Gábor Schmidt – Imre Tóth, 561 pages

Fülöpháza, March 6, 2025.

Csaba Kiss

Chief Executive Officer

Kiss Kertész Duó Kft